

FAIR and Open Non-Traditional Research Outputs Project Report

Key Project Information

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“It would actually be nice if there was even a place just to understand maybe what some other institutions are doing, so that there is language and I could go to my institution and say, do you do this because I think at this point, I don't even know what to ask for. So if that was something that would be possible, that would be lovely.” - Researcher interviewee

Executive summary

In November 2021 CAUL undertook to extend its Advancing Open Scholarship program with a study of library support for Non-Traditional Research Outputs (NTROs). A multi-institutional working group was formed to examine current practice. Activities included a literature review, an environmental scan of Australian and international libraries, a survey of all Australian and New Zealand academic libraries and a series of interviews with experts, librarians and researchers.

The literature review revealed issues around the term NTRo, particularly given its positioning in relation to “traditional” research outputs; questions about the value of NTRo; the role of the Institutional Repository and how they support these outputs to be open; the kind of expectations that researchers bring to the management of NTRo, particularly in the way they are presented and made accessible; some of the challenges they pose and how these differ from that of traditional outputs; questions about the research content of these outputs and the strong connections between NTRo and Indigenous knowledge issues.

The environmental scan of Australian and International academic libraries looked at evidence for library support of NTRo. The scan indicated the need for more work the development of library support for FAIR and Open NTRo. Most mention of NTRo was found in different online research guides (libguides) and most mention of FAIR or CARE principles concerned research data management.

We conducted a survey of all Australian and New Zealand academic libraries asking about both the broader university context as well as different aspects of library support. This revealed some continuing questions around the publication of NTRo and the kind of incentives available to make them open. The survey also revealed strong library focus in support of NTRo as part of the then ERA process. It asked about the type, volume and schemas used within the Institutional Repositories. Finally, the survey reported on support for researchers in the area of Creative Commons, FAIR principles, copyright, impact and the application of metadata.

The project received ethics advice and approval from the RMIT University DSC College Human Ethics Advisory Network (CHEAN) to conduct interviews with different stakeholder groups. The interviews with experts revealed significant issues with the term NTRo, the value of NTRo, the complications of copyright, the infrastructure and systems to support them, along with discoverability and re-use aspects. They also noted how the open agenda was only starting to engage these types of output and how FAIR principles were only partially applicable to NTRo. These interviews also suggested that the move beyond the traditional research paradigm had a strong connection to Indigenous knowledge issues. There was a significant emphasis on the need to be inclusive in referring to research outputs in policy and guidance and to improve the systems and infrastructure supporting them.

The interviews with researchers confirmed significant reticence about the term NTRo and how it positioned such research as non-standard. They also highlighted the amount of “red tape” associated with demonstrating the research content of NTRo, the variety of formats, authorship and intellectual property issues, and the repositories and platforms supporting them. These interviews also explored the complications of publishing and promoting NTRo and the diversity of audiences for these outputs. The interviews revealed how

researchers look to libraries for support in areas like researcher profiles, FAIR principles, metrics, copyright, the repository and support for graduate researchers. There was less awareness that libraries could assist in areas such as metadata, DOIs, providing evidence of impact and engagement, archiving and preservation, and access issues.

Finally we conducted interviews with different libraries as a follow up to the survey. These discussions revealed copyright as an important area of library support for NTROs, particularly with regard to making them open. This included multiple copyrights and third-party material, along with licensing and re-use issues. Some libraries were seeking to improve the workflows around submission of NTROs, including as part of the then ERA process. There was some concern at the resource intensive nature of support because of the complications of NTROs. Libraries reported the usefulness of having wider guidelines and direction from the Institution in developing this area, including improvement of support for the researchers. Libraries were still developing approaches to Indigenous knowledge issues associated with NTROs.

The information elicited in the literature review, scan, survey and interviews was used to draw out some broad themes which then informed the development of the framework. The framework is intended to provide guidance for CAUL member institutions on how to increase the proportion of NTROs by Australian university researchers that are appropriately described, archived, preserved, made accessible and promoted. It is organised around issues grouped into different phases of the research lifecycle and identifies aims, enablement activities and tiered services. The framework is structured to allow libraries to adopt different aspects according to levels of interest, maturity and resources.

In addition to adoption of the Framework the project suggests the following overall recommendations for the sector:

- Adoption of a broad and inclusive definition of NTROs.
- Adoption of conception of FAIR and CARE that looks beyond research data to research outputs in general.
- Promote the idea of research output management plans beyond just RDM.
- Contribute to the ongoing development of protocols for libraries in handling research outputs related to Indigenous knowledge that encompass authorship, citation, repository presentation, copyright, licensing, access.
- Facilitate discussion of repository requirements for managing and presenting NTROs.
- Consider strategies to facilitate development of national collection of NTROs.
- Development of collective resources, e.g. guides across universities in support of NTROs.
- Facilitate cross sector conversation of FAIR, CARE and open as applies to NTROs, eg community of practice conversation.
- Lobby ORCID to improve their management of NTROs.

Introduction

Background

CAUL'S Advancing Open Scholarship Program is focussed on reaching beyond libraries and the higher education sector to advocate for a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (FAIR) strategy for Australia. To date, the program has largely focused on publications and data. This project takes the opportunity to extend this work to explore the role of libraries beyond the management of open publications and data to the area of Non-Traditional Research Outputs (NTROs). It aims to provide guidance to CAUL member institutions in developing services and support for researchers producing NTROs.

There has not been any sector-level work on the role of libraries in ensuring that FAIR principles are applied to NTROs (e.g. film, creative writing, website design). This exploratory project sought to address this gap by investigating current practice, including areas where there are opportunities to improve or expand practice related to application of the FAIR and open principles to NTROs. The project has also sought to explore how the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles should be applied to these outputs.

The CARE Principles, which complement the FAIR principles in the area of research data, raise important issues in the treatment of NTROs. These principles posit that research must enable Indigenous Peoples to derive benefits, that Indigenous Peoples' rights and interests in Indigenous research be recognised, that those working with Indigenous People have a responsibility to show how research outputs are used to support Indigenous Peoples' self-determination and collective benefit, and that Indigenous Peoples' rights and wellbeing should be the primary concern at all stages of the research lifecycle.

Project objectives

The project objectives have been to:

1. Explore the roles academic libraries can or should play in supporting NTROs, including describing, archiving, preserving, facilitating discovery and access, supporting publication and promotion, and providing evidence of impact.
2. Develop a framework for academic libraries that describes how libraries can apply FAIR and CARE principles to NTROs.

Scope

The scope of the project included aspects of dealing with NTROs that are relevant to libraries, specifically, description, archiving, preservation, discovery and access, publication and promotion, and providing evidence of impact.

Specific technical considerations that are generally outside the responsibility of the library were deemed out of scope, e.g., data storage space.

NTROs have been strongly associated with the national research assessment programs Excellence in Research for Australia (ERA) and Engagement and Impact (EI). As of the time of writing these programs were under review and we have chosen to include discussion and comments around these programs .

Approach

The project sought to identify gaps in current practice and potential areas for improvement. This is a nascent area of interest without extensive studies of this type within the current literature. The project therefore undertook a number of activities designed to explore the emerging issues.

Literature review, environmental scan, survey

In its initial stages the project undertook a literature review of published material related to library treatment of FAIR and Open NTRs. This raised issues around terminology, the recognition of NTRs as research outputs, the role of institutional repositories, researcher concerns and expectations, challenges and responses, FAIR principles, research statements and research impact, and Indigenous knowledge issues.

The project then undertook an environmental scan of all CAUL member libraries (in Australia and New Zealand) looking at evidence of support provided for NTRs. We sought to examine mention of NTRs on websites, institutional repositories, policy documents and online guides; how NTRs were defined; mention of FAIR, CARE and open; repository and other digital platforms' collection policies; support for NTRs and Indigenous knowledge; reference to other parts of the university supporting NTRs; reference to other policies or guidelines; contacts for guidance and assistance.

The project then developed a survey that was sent to all CAUL member libraries. The survey contained 37 questions and was divided into broad areas covering the wider university context, the library's role in supporting NTRs, issues arising from institutional repository support for NTRs, researcher needs, and items for inclusion in a potential framework. The survey received 34 responses.

Interviews with experts/stakeholders, researchers and libraries

Given the exploratory nature of the project, designed to tap into participant experience and perceptions, the project chose to take a qualitative approach to data collection. In-depth, semi-structured interviews were designed to allow the project to tap into participants' experiences and explore emergent themes. The interviews with experts/stakeholders were designed to further explore the broader contextual issues. Interviews with researchers were intended to identify the types of support needed by researchers working in this area. The interviews with libraries were designed to follow up on the survey and produce a more detailed understanding of current practices within academic libraries in support of NTRs. The interviews included exploration of the extent to which FAIR and CARE principles have been applied to this area.

The project employed a broad thematic analysis in analysing the interview data. After transcriptions were reviewed and corrected, they were used to identify different themes relevant to thinking about library services and these were then summarised within a descriptive analysis document. This then informed the development of the framework.

Ethics

The project worked with the DSC College Human Ethics Advisory Network (CHEAN) at RMIT University to get approval for the study. The initial ethics application was classed as low risk.

The ethics application sought approval for research activity involving semi-structured, in-depth interviews with the three cohorts:

1. 6 key stakeholders in open research and scholarly communications advocacy in Australia
2. 10-12 researchers from Australian universities who produce NTRs
3. 6 research support staff from Australian university libraries.

The recruitment of experts/stakeholders was selected from suggestions provided by CAUL and from the project team's own knowledge. These included experts or people from representative bodies in areas such as

open access research, FAIR principles, creative research, etc. Researchers were selected from staff at Australian universities involved in research that produces NTROs. Library staff were selected from research support staff working at Australian university libraries. Research participants were recruited via email invitation.

Participants were given a Participant Information and Consent Form with the consent form returned prior to the interview. All interviews were conducted, recorded and transcribed using Microsoft Teams. Interviews ran for approximately 60 minutes. Recordings and transcriptions were stored on Cloudstor. Once transcriptions were reviewed against recordings, the recordings were deleted and all identifying information was removed from transcriptions. Each transcription was stored using a unique seven digit code in case the interviewee wished to withdraw data from the project. The project intended from the outset to share de-identified transcriptions in accordance with good open and FAIR data management practice.

When approved by DSC College Human Ethics Advisory Network (CHEAN) at RMIT University, the application was then passed onto institutions of all research team members for their information.

A revised version of the application was submitted to allow for interviewing two to three Indigenous researchers. The project decided not to include the interviewing of Indigenous researchers in the initial application until the project could be reviewed by the newly-formed CAUL Indigenous Knowledges Advisory Group. Despite many requests across the country we weren't able to secure these interviews.

Framework development

The starting point in the development of the framework was to think about the process across each of the phases of the research lifecycle. The project group used the data from the literature review, scan, survey and interviews to develop the areas of focus for the framework and accompanying aims and tiered services. It became evident that there were also issues of enablement and advocacy that it would be useful to identify in facilitating the development of the service. It was then sent out for feedback which was reviewed line by line for change and improvement.

One of the prominent themes of the feedback was that information was overwhelming and there was a lack of guidance about where to start. This led the project group to include maturity levels within the framework as well as descriptions of how these levels operate. They also incorporated a suggestion from one of the readings in the literature review that suggested the broad phases of Pre-Production, Production and Post-Production as a way of framing NTROs.

Literature review

Terminology

The term Non-Traditional Research Outputs (NTRs) emerges from a decades-long argument about the value of creative arts research in producing new knowledge and contributing to scholarship (Neil et al., 2022). Bronwen Neil et al note the quaintness of the term as opposed to “traditional outputs” (Neil et al., 2022). Amanda Lawrence notes the importance of research reports and different types of papers to research and development, and argues that despite this, these are often overlooked and undervalued as research outputs. She sees this reflected in the lack of adequate terminology with terms like “grey literature”, “non-traditional research outputs” and “unpublished literature” (Lawrence, 2021). Similarly, Neil et al. note that despite being ARC-funded, NTRs are undervalued and therefore rated less than traditional text-based publications within the ERA process. Amongst other things, this raises questions about the capacity of researchers to articulate research contribution and the capacity of evaluators to recognise that contribution (Neil et al., 2022).

Recognition and legitimacy

According to the Library Publishing Research Committee, the distinction between traditional and non-traditional publishing is sometimes regarded as a distinction between formal and informal publishing, or may be seen as an issue of the particular forms the research output takes. There are also complications with certain outputs not having a clear end or finish date, or clear distinctions between different versions and editions (Library Publishing Research Committee, 2020, 11-12). For the Library Publishing Research Committee, these difficulties are raised by library publishing activity and the desire to ensure NTRs are regarded as legitimate research outputs (2020, 12).

The issue may derive partly from what we regard as constituting legitimate publishing. Lawrence believes that the diversity of research publishing practices, involving non-commercial and informal activities, has been obscured by the dominance of mainstream academic publishing (Lawrence, 2021). She points out that new digital technologies have seen research content take a variety of forms and made available via a variety of channels. In this context, we should conceive of publishing in its broadest sense ‘to make public’ rather than conflate it with the market-based publishing industry (Lawrence 2021). This underlines the importance of NTRs in the area of open research.

The role of repositories

Robin Burgess points to the important role of institutional repositories in underpinning the validity of research outputs in areas such as the visual arts (Burgess, 2019, 37). Burgess points to the benefits of placing NTRs in repositories and notes how good curation and management further allows the meeting of funder requirements; addressing discoverability and loss issues; allowing for the testing of reliability of research; facilitating tracking and impact; facilitating collaborative opportunities (Burgess, 2019, 37). Lambria also notes that repositories facilitate accessibility to the wider public; promote work being done in the fine arts; and connect the work which is often on personal websites with institutional legitimacy (Lambria, 2020, 9-11). Anne Shelley cites the enhanced visibility given to these outputs by repositories (Shelley, 2020, 132-33). Niamh Quigley et al. see the benefits of visibility being discoverability, opportunities for collaboration, timesaving, the meeting of funder requirements, and institutional endorsement. They also see benefits to the institution in facilitating re-use, diversity of impacts, preservation of outputs, along with evoking discussion, support for teaching, and promotion of schools and faculties (Quigley et al., 2022, 8).

Despite this, NTRs are not generally a significant part of the institutional repository collections. In 2019 it was reported that in the University of Queensland Repository 0.6% of items were NTRs (Marrington 2019). A study by Quigley et al. notes that creative practice researchers are committed to sharing their work beyond the university via a variety of different types of website, social media and other channels. They also note that the system of rewards and recognition for these researchers lay outside the university system. The problem here was that this activity remained largely invisible to the institution’s systems and therefore was difficult to

capture adequately. They suggest this disconnect may be a factor in the low level of items in the institutional repository (Quigley et al., 2022, 4, 13).

Researcher concerns and expectations

Kate Lambria notes the lack of material in repositories due to artist concern about making their works openly accessible, lack of understanding or promotion of repositories in the arts areas, and uncertainty about whether the repository can display the material (Lambria, 2020, 2). Lambria further notes that arts researchers expressed concern about others gaining financially through the appropriation of their works; concern that others might repurpose the work and claim ownership over it; concerns about copyright and lack of knowledge of its procedures; concern about ownership of works that are the product of a collaborative team; and concern about administrative burden of submitting items to the repository (Lambria, 2020, 11-13). Shelley cites “permissions culture” and lack of consensus about sharing images online (Shelley, 2020, 132). She also raises the issue of how the display of different file types is less than ideal (Shelley, 2020, 132). Quigley et al. find that researchers regard adding creative research outputs to their institutional repository to be laborious and confusing and have difficulty with the lack of functionality. There is also a low awareness of the repository in general, lack of understanding of its purpose, and low awareness of its preservation function (Quigley et al., 2022, 4, 13-14). This leads them to explore alternative platforms (Quigley et al., 2022, 4).

In this context, Lambria usefully examines the kind of expectations that creative arts researchers hold. This includes control over the curation of their work, especially with regard to the different aspects arising from educational and professional settings; making connections between different online platforms to reduce the need to upload to several areas; library assistance on issues such as author rights and file types; and the need for developed online presence and profile (Lambria, 2020, 13-14). Quigley et al. note how researchers desire systems that are relevant to creative practice researchers. They want to add outputs to their academic and ORCID profile that can be used for grants applications. They wish to be able to add metadata that adequately reflects significance and impact (Quigley et al., 2022, 4, 7).

Shelley notes how repositories have not met expectations in terms of submission of open access items by researchers (Shelley, 2020, 133). Interestingly, she points to some discussion around rethinking the mission of the institutional repository to focus purely on NTRs (Shelley, 2020, 134). Burgess suggests we look at the “visual impact” of institutional repositories expected by arts researchers (Burgess, 2019, 38). Lambria talks about effective ways of promoting the repository to faculty including enhancement of online profile of the faculty, especially for early career researchers helping promote the faculty to potential students, and making it more visible to the rest of the university. She notes the need to work with researchers around copyright issues, deposit options, licensing options, and collaboration. She recommends attention to workflows to streamline collection and deposit processes. Finally, she calls for appreciation of curation issues and managing works that researchers may not want to share because of the impact on their professional lives (Lambria, 2020, 14-16). Similarly, Quigley et al. call for improvement of workflows and systems integrations as a means to encourage creative practice researchers to include their work in the repository (Quigley et al., 2022, 4). They also advocate showcasing of creative practice awards and highlighting best practice examples (Quigley et al., 2022, 21).

Challenges and responses

Some of the issues and challenges for repositories include the way these outputs often involve multiple items; that they are the product of both collaborative and independent work; that the work is sometimes already accessible online; how they raise the need to navigate access management that allows promotion while also addressing concern about items being reproduced; the complexity of size and scale issues involved; copyright complexities that stem from the particular forms of collaboration; and the need for metadata that contextualises the work (Burgess, 2019, 37).

Works of art possibly also need a more extensive metadata schema e.g., multimedia items require more descriptive data than books or journals. According to Burgess this might include “time period, dimensions,

orientation, techniques used, style or period, cultural context, inscriptions, conservation treatment, etc” (Burgess, 2019, 37). Burgess notes a study of NTROs at Goldsmith’s University that recommended institutional repositories use common terms and descriptions, include a glossary, include additional metadata, and provide clear guidance (Burgess, 2019, 37-8). In 2019, the University of Queensland Library undertook a project to review the capture of creative works. This saw the development of a “suite of new work type forms in five major ERA categories” and “enrichment of the metadata schema to support decision making about the significance and ‘quality’ of an output” (Marrington, 2019). Quigley et. al. undertook a card sort activity on appropriate metadata among creative researchers. In an examination of dramatic works, the system they examined lacked metadata detail for the duration, multiple performances, awards, or reviews - all of which goes to significance and impact. It also lacked the ability to add awards or prizes once the record had been created (Quigley et al., 2022, 14).

Shelley suggests dividing management of repository projects into three phases: Firstly, the pre-production phase, which includes decisions about copyright, scope, size, timeline, file size, naming conventions, metadata, access levels, roles and responsibilities, and desired appearance of the collection. Next is the production phase that sees scanning, file processing, uploading, and quality control. Finally, the post production phase sees reviewing and publishing, archiving, description, and recording usage data (Shelley, 2020, 134-36).

FAIR principles

There has also been some important local work by the FAIR4RS group reported by Chue Hong et al. on the application of FAIR principles (which proposes to make outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) to software. This work is intended to “increase the transparency, reproducibility, and reusability of research” (Chue et al., 2022, 4).

Giglia et al. note the need to widen the scope of FAIR principles for areas like the digital humanities (Giglia et al., 2021, 22). The FAIR4RS work identifies issues around FAIR that may have relevance to a consideration of NTROs in general. They identify the need for persistent identifiers, the description of rich metadata, retrievability via standard and open protocols that include authentication, the inclusion of programming interfaces (APIs) to facilitate interoperability, relevant and accurate descriptions of attributes, clear and appropriate licences, detailed provenance information and reference to other relevant outputs (Chue et al., 2022, 7-13).

Giglia et al. note that FAIR awareness is still low and there is still uneven use of identifiers, metadata, interoperability standards and open licensing. They note the diversity and complexity of the humanities and social sciences environment which precludes a single approach or standard. They note legal challenges associated with sensitive information and property rights that come from re-use of these outputs. They also discuss the need for incentives (Giglia et al. 2021, 23) Giglia et al. further discuss the need for advocacy and training around FAIR, to coordinate all relevant groups, including the library, in the management of FAIR (Giglia et al. 2021, 22, 24).

Research statements and research impact

Another response to the long process to have NTROs recognised as research outputs includes a focus on the research statement. This is also of interest to libraries that provide or collaborate with those that provide research writing support. Quigley et al. note that the writing of a research statement is a further blockage to submitting items to a research management system for creative researchers (Quigley et al., 2022, 13). According to Paul Williams, research statements allow the creative researcher to “justify, situate and contextualise their creative works as measurable research outputs.” Williams advocates an approach likely to engage creative practitioners in drawing attention to the research statement’s touchpoints with the literary manifesto, albeit recognising that the statement places distinct emphasis on accountability (Williams, 2022).

A further issue of interest to libraries concerns the provision of evidence of research impact. Zhao and Minns (2019) discuss impact in the creative arts areas as being more than simply citation based metrics but broader

social, economic and cultural impact, including performances, exhibitions etc (Zhao & Minns, 2019). They point out that many academics are unsure about how the library might assist them in this area. As a result they advise addressing this specifically with tailored workshops, along with working collaboratively with researchers to develop knowledge of creative disciplines (Zhao & Minns, 2019).

Indigenous knowledge

Non-traditional research also has a particular importance in the area of Indigenous knowledge although the literature addressing this issue is still underdeveloped. Edwina Howell points to its importance in building the track record and grant strategy for the Aboriginal History Archive project (Howell, 2018, 140). She notes that non-Indigenous researchers working in this area need a high level of reflexivity around motivations, expectations, benefits, and accountability (Howell, 140). There are now several university guides for NTROs. The guide produced by the University of Sydney points out that research involving Indigenous knowledge is not easily captured in traditional forms. It further refers to the way Indigenous research is embedded in Indigenous knowing, being and doing. It is often co-created with Indigenous communities and disseminated in embodied forms negotiated between the researcher and community. There is an overarching principle that it be to the benefit of communities and wellbeing of participants (University of Sydney, 2021, 4).

Environmental scan

The University context

The environmental scan began by looking at the wider university context, where NTROs are sometimes mentioned in different policy documents, including research policy, open access policy, although not uniformly. Some universities have developed some general guidelines for managing NTROs, e.g. [University of Sydney](#), [University of Newcastle](#), [University of New England](#), [Charles Sturt](#). There is also some guidance on NTROs as part of ERA submission, e.g. a knowledge base of articles at the University of Sydney.

At the time when these were reviewed, there were several institutional open access policies that make limited mention of NTROs:

- Latrobe included NTROs in the purpose section covering publication and dissemination of outputs;
- University Technology Sydney, the Australian Catholic University, University of Adelaide and Griffith University included NTROs in a list of definitions covering a scholarly work;
- University of New England included them both in the scope and definitions;
- The University of Tasmania's open access procedure flagged use of alternative metadata for NTROs;
- The University of Adelaide policy encouraged the depositing of NTROs into the repository and The University of New South Wales included them as part of the outputs available in the repository.
- Only the University of Melbourne goes beyond these limited mentions to acknowledge some difficulties associated with copyright and licensing in making these research outputs open.

Library mention of NTROs

In the main, there was little explicit mention of NTROs within the research sections of university library websites. The most obvious mention of NTROs occurred on different Libguides. This included guides covering researcher profiles, altmetrics, strategic publishing, creative research, open access publishing and research impact. This was not uniform, however, and many libraries offering these kinds of guides did not mention NTROs. Examples of research guides providing advice on research impact for NTROs can be found at the [University of Melbourne](#), [RMIT](#) and [Deakin](#). The RMIT [creative practice guide](#) includes information on writing NTRo statements.

There was also some mention of NTROs with repository information, e.g. in FAQ sections or where it mentions output types or submission guidelines. The VU Research Repository Open Access Policy refers to "creative works with a research component." There is also sometimes information provided in relation to resources such as Figshare.com.

Defining NTROs

In many instances NTROs were either not defined or the reader was referred to the ERA definition. There was a range of other definitions and summaries of what constitutes NTROs:

- RMIT's Open Access Publishing guide asserts that NTROs include "data sets, conference posters, government or non-governmental reports or policy documents, recordings of presentations, etc."
- Charles Sturt University's Repository defines creative outputs according to textual and non-textual outputs.
- The University of Sydney guide says: "Non-traditional research outputs' (NTROs) comprises a wide variety of other outputs that differ in their form and mode of production and are classified differently for administrative purposes. NTROs may include anything from highly experimental works of creative art – music or visual art, for example, creative writing, dance or design – through to scholarly editions

and translations, ethnographic recordings, website creation, outputs co-created with Indigenous communities, and commissioned reports for government or non-government bodies.”

- The Curtin University strategic publishing guide notes: “Not all research output takes the form of journals articles, books, book chapters or conference papers. Some researchers consult with government or private organisations to produce reports in their area of expertise, others create research datasets, software code or 3D images. Humanities and social sciences researchers produce outputs such as live performances, curated exhibitions and original creative works.”
- The University of Adelaide gives examples of creative works, software or computer code.

Mention of FAIR, CARE or Open

At the time of review, open research was sometimes featured as an option within the research sections of the library websites, but NTROs didn’t feature strongly as part of this. FAIR and CARE principles were usually mentioned as part of research data management. The former was more prominent than the latter. FAIR was not always mentioned as an aspect of open more generally and usually only briefly. Information on FAIR usually did not mention NTROs. FAIR was mentioned in the UTAS Repository information, however this was not always the case at different libraries.

Mention of Library role in supporting NTROs

There was sometimes mention of library support for open access and FAIR principles, but generally little information on the library’s role in supporting NTROs. UTAS open access procedures mention library assistance with copyright issues. At the time of the scan, Griffith University Library advertised a copyright workshop for research in the creative and performing arts. Repository information sometimes mentioned support for submitting creative works and reports. UQ Repository had information on staff assistance with permissions and mention that preservation was not guaranteed with different file types. James Cook included a [publishing guide](#) with exemplars on writing research statements for NTROs.

There was little reference to other parts of the university supporting NTROs in the publicly available information. There were some limited references where the university had a NTRO guideline or to ERA submission guidelines or to policies such as those concerning open access. Contacts vary from no explicit contact for NTRO support to contact in the research publications area or the general research office contact. Within the library, it varied between the repository and the general research services area.

Repository support for NTROs

At the time of the scan, most repositories didn’t have publicly accessible collection policies that included extended mention of NTROs. Exceptions included [James Cook](#) and Griffith University’s [collection statement for its Research Repository](#). As mentioned above, repositories frequently referred to NTROs as output types and within submission information. Charles Sturt University Library has a [guide to submitting creative works](#).

RMIT has a creative practice guide that refers to putting NTROs into Figshare. Monash uses Figshare for publishing research data and NTROs. The University of Adelaide uses Figshare as its data and digital object repository and makes reference to adding “figures, datasets, software/code, images, videos, posters and presentations.”

Indigenous knowledge

There was no evidence of information on NTROs and Indigenous knowledge from the scan. At the time of review, this still seemed to be an underdeveloped and emergent area within libraries. There was some evidence of sessions provided on Indigenous knowledge issues and some general information on Libguides. Some information was provided by The University of Adelaide Library on their Indigenous [knowledge](#) page as part of their research support information. The University of Sydney had some more general [cultural protocols](#) for its collections that mention FAIR and CARE.

Survey

Research

The survey received 34 responses from those sent out to university libraries across Australia and New Zealand.

NTROs

Recognition

On the question of recognition of NTROs within the university most institutions (73.53%) report that they are regarded as very legitimate. This is reflected in the way NTROs feature (85.29%) in policies, principles, procedures and guidance statements.

Types of NTROs

The most common types of NTROs mentioned include creative works (11.3%), performance (10.96%), recorded works (10.96%), curated exhibitions and events (10.62%), rendered works (9.59%), research reports (8.9%) and commissioned reports (8.56%). There were also portfolios (7.88%), software (6.51%), websites (5.14%), code (4.11%) and databases (2.74%). A range of other types of material were mentioned under the "other" category.

Publishing

On the question of how NTROs are published and made visible, the most common destination identified in the responses was the institutional repository as well as submission to publication management systems. There was mention from one institution of work with arts faculties to streamline the workflow to facilitate this. These would be then pushed out to researcher and academic profiles. There was also some specific mention of utilising Figshare.com for creative outputs and NTROs. Several respondents indicated that it was largely up to the individual researcher and that there tended to be no standard way of publishing NTROs. Other platforms included faculty and institutional websites, video platforms like YouTube, collaborative sites created between partner institutions, GitHub and ResearchGate.

Open access

On whether there was an emphasis in the university on making NTROs open access, the most common answer was 'no' (64.71%). For those that answered 'yes', this was emphasised via open access policies or via outreach activities initiated by the library. One respondent indicated that even with the latter, this mainly focused on traditional outputs. Open access is not generally a criteria used for promotions or performance reviews. One response noted that open access for NTROs was sometimes limited by performing rights, commercial representation and copyright. There was also a question about whether NTROs figure strongly in ARC funding and whether compliance with open access applies as strongly in this area.

Incentives

Most institutions reported (91.18%) that there were no incentives to make NTROs open access. The few that did mention incentives (8.82%) referred to the open access policy recognising NTROs, recognition within academic promotion workshops and their recognition as research activity. In one case, NTROs could be made available in the repository if made open access.

The Library

Supporting NTROs

44.12% of respondents reported that the library had a role in the collection of research outputs for Excellence for Research in Australia (ERA). 73.53% of libraries reported working with the research office on initiatives related to NTROs. This work involved attendance at ERA strategy meetings (including an NTRo working group); support for the ERA process; review and improvement to NTRo reporting; validation of research outputs (including metadata and publication date); assistance in the collection and curation of full-text outputs nominated for inclusion in the ERA peer review samples; contribution towards NTRo guidelines; enhancing

NTRO metadata entry into the repository; ensuring the entry was searchable in the library discovery platform; increasing exposure of outputs; increasing the number of NTROs reviewed and eligible for ERA; general liaison, including back to the researchers; collaboration on workflows, education and promotion; joint work in support of research statements; and development of a creative showcase platform.

Policies and procedures

There were 70.59% who reported that NTROs were mentioned by libraries in policies, principles, procedures and other guidance statements. The project group was provided with links or the names of these documents.

Indigenous knowledge

Only 11.76% of libraries reported having guidelines that cover Indigenous knowledge issues associated with making NTROs FAIR and open. A couple of respondents mentioned that Indigenous knowledge was referred to in research data guides. There was mention of an internal guide that referred to the AIATSIS Guidelines for Ethical Research - particularly Principle 13 on managing terms of use, access and storage of research. There was also mention here of the importance of informed consent and reviewing access conditions into the future with key stakeholders, platforms designed to share results with Indigenous communities, and Creative Commons licensing that included Indigenous knowledge labels.

The Institutional Repository

NTROs

On the question of what is stored on the institutional repository, apart from traditional research outputs, the breakdown is metadata only entries for NTROs (27.78%), born digital NTROs (27.78%), digitised versions or recordings of NTROs that are not born digital (25%) and research data (19.44%).

Systems and holdings

On the question of repositories or systems institutions have apart from the main institutional repository, responses were a separate repository containing metadata for NTROs (13.04%), a separate repository containing born digital NTROs (13.04%), a separate repository containing digitised versions or recordings of NTROs (13.04%), a separate repository for research data (36.95%), a separate repository for research software or code (10.87%), a system used to showcase NTROs (e.g. Omeka) (13.04%).

On the question of whether repositories contain items apart from theses and ERA assessable items 76.57 % responded affirmatively and 23.33% negatively.

On the question of whether NTROs not available open access are stored on the repository 58.8% responded affirmatively and 41.18% negatively.

Collection policies

On the question of whether repositories containing NTROs have collection policies 67.65% responded affirmatively and 32.35% negatively. Links were provided to these policies. On the research outputs listed in the policy, respondents also listed these types of NTROs,

- ERA eligible categories
- Creative works with a research component, live performance of creative works (portfolios of creative works - recorded/rendered creative works - substantial curated or produced public exhibitions and events), recorded/rendered creative works and curated or produced substantial public exhibitions and events, images, music recordings,
- Technical reports, commissioned reports and other types of research reports, student reports, working papers, seminar papers, presentations and discussion papers.
- Research donated by departments to the library,

- Final state research data outputs associated with grant-funded research and with manuscripts and journals that have a data policy, data related to student research.
- Open access 'grey literature'

Resource types

On the question of resource type categories used by repositories to display NTRs there were different types of listings given, varying in degree of breakdown into specific forms. Some examples included:

- Creative work; Event; Performance; Recorded work; Report.
- Collection; dataset; design; essay; event; interactive resource; moving image; musical score; patent; poem; sculpture; software; sound; still image; working papers; reports.
- Original creative work – Visual art work Original creative work – Design/Architectural work Original creative work – Textual work Original creative work – Other Live performance of creative work – Music Live performance of creative work – Play Live performance of creative work – Dance Live performance of creative work – Other Recorded/rendered creative work – Audio/visual recording Recorded/rendered creative work – Performance Recorded/rendered creative work – Inter-arts Recorded/rendered creative work – Digital creative work Recorded/rendered creative work – Website/web based exhibition Recorded/rendered creative work – Other Public exhibition or event – Web based exhibition Public exhibition or event – Exhibition/Event Public exhibition or event – Festival Public exhibition or event – Other Research report for external bodies – Public sector Research report for external bodies – Industry Research report for external bodies – Not for profit Research report for external bodies – Other We don't use all these types for public presentation – they're simplified mainly to one of three types: exhibition, report, or creative work.

Volume and metadata

On the question of how many NTRs are included in the institutional repository, these ranged between 50 and several thousand. On the question of whether metadata information is different for these outputs than traditional research outputs 39.39% responded in the affirmative and 60.61% responded in the negative. The metadata elements were again various with some giving metadata that were specific to NTRs. Examples included:

- Fields in Symplectic Elements or Figshare (e.g. size of work or duration; location; medium);
- Format, size, duration, event date, start date, finish date, event type, event location.
- Elements that may be used in our NTR metadata include: Title – Contributors with role and affiliation – Year of publication/presentation – Publisher and place of publication (if published) – Size – Physical description – Language – Abstract – Keyword subjects – Resource type – Name, location and dates of event or exhibition – Commissioning body – Parent publication – Research statement – Field of research codes – Peer review status

Schema

There were 17.65% of libraries reporting they had adopted an existing metadata schema for NTRs, 29.41% of libraries reported that they had adapted an existing schema and 52.94% reported they had done neither of these. Dublin Core was the schema most had adopted with only one reporting that they adopted MODS. Dublin Core also featured strongly among those adapted but there was also mention of ERA SEER XML, DC terms, Figshare, Esploro, MARC21/RDA standards. Only 2.94% of libraries reported creating a metadata schema for NTRs.

Supporting researchers

Creative Commons

There were 85.29% of libraries reporting that they assisted researchers with Creative Commons licences with 14.71% stating they did not.

FAIR

On the question of whether libraries support and promote the application of FAIR principles to NTRs, the most prominent responses are

- Knowledge of FAIR principles: 45.45% provide resources and 36.3% provide advice
- Open access publishing: 38.24% provide training and 35.35% provide advice
- Research profiles: 40.63% provide training and 25% provide advice
- Licences and copyright: 51.52% provide advice and 27.27% provide training
- Applying metadata in repositories: 41.94% do it for them and 19.35% provide advice and 19.35% provide resources
- Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI; use of, provision of): 52.94% do it for them and 38.24% provide advice
- Publication: 41.94% provide advice and 29.03% provide resources
- Preservation of access: 50% provide advice and 40.63% do it for them
- Levels of access (e.g. restricted, embargos): 57.58% do it for them and 33.33% provide advice
- Ensure NTRs are indexed in Google, Trove etc: 81.82% do it for them and 15.15% provide advice.

Researchers and FAIR

On the question of issues in supporting researchers to make their NTRs FAIR and open, respondents nominated items from the following list:

- Copyright 10.88%
- Physical nature of some research outputs 9.62%
- Measuring impact 8.37%
- Versions and iterations 8.37%
- Combination of collaborative work and individual work 7.53%
- Capturing size and scale of the work 7.53%
- Archiving and long term preservation 7.53%
- NTRs sometimes have associated documents describing and explaining the research content 7.11%
- NTRs often involve multiple items 6.69%
- Quality of reproduction 6.69%
- The work may already be accessible online 6.28%
- Application of metadata standards 6.28%
- Other, please list 7.11%

The “other” issues mentioned included demand too low to provide/develop specific support; time and money; platforms unsuitable; cultural appropriateness; difficulties around permissions; contractual obligations; confidentiality issues; IP issues; workflow issues; incentives.

Significant issues

When asked to nominate three areas from a list that were the most significant issues in supporting researchers to make NTROs FAIR and open, responses indicated the following in order of prominence:

- Copyright 22.55%
- Archiving and long term preservation 12.75%
- Measuring impact 11.76%
- Combination of collaborative work and individual work 9.80%
- Physical nature of some research outputs 8.82%
- Capturing size and scale of the work 5.88%
- Application of metadata standards 5.88%
- NTROs often involve multiple items 5.88%
- Versions and iterations 4.90%
- Other 4.90%
- NTROs sometimes have associated documents describing and explaining the research content 2.94%
- Quality of reproduction 2.94%
- The work may already be accessible online 0.98%

“Other” items included time, cultural appropriateness, confidentiality, and suitable platforms.

Other areas

When asked about other things the library does to support researchers to make NTROs open and FAIR responses included:

- Consultation and advice service
- Promotion of FAIR and OA in research guides and videos,
- Targeted presentations and workshops in support of NTROs
- Support for creators/authors who deposit their NTROs in the institutional repository
- Provision of tailored OA platform for NTROs
- Development of workflows and processes for describing NTROs
- Utilising Research specialist librarians as strong advocates for FAIR and open
- Support for persistent identifiers including a DOI minting service
- Creative residence program for specific projects.
- Events like Open Access Week.
- Representation on university working groups and committees where we highlight need to consider FAIR/open for all outputs including NTROs
- Project looking at library support for creative and practice-based research
- Collaboration with other areas of the university on workflows
- Copyright support
- Creative Commons support

Support areas

When asked to choose from a list of items, respondents nominated the following as areas of advice, support or training:

- Copyright advice 15.57%
- Evidencing the impact of their NTROs 14.62%
- Application of metadata to their research outputs 13.21%
- The application of NTROs to researcher profiles (e.g. ORCID) 11.79%
- Use of persistent identifiers 11.79%
- Preservation and archiving 10.85%
- Support for publication and promotion of NTROs 10.38%
- Assistance with development of research statements for NTROs 10.38%
- Other (free text) 1.42%

The “Other” items included how to support NTRO researchers to understand what is research and what is not; how to describe and articulate the research component; planning and providing evidence of impact; writing research statements; understanding CC licences; and ensuring cultural appropriateness.

The Framework

When asked to rate degree of importance for items that might be included in a framework, the following was registered:

- Licencing: 76.47% very important
- Copyright: 70.59% very important
- Evidencing the impact of NTROs: 64.71% very important
- Assigning permanent unique identifiers: 64.71% very important
- Measuring impact of NTROs: 58.82% very important
- Supporting sharing and reuse of NTROs: 58.82% very important
- Supporting publication and promotion of NTROs: 50% very important
- Managing versions and iterations: 47.06% very important
- Long term preservation: 47.06% very important
- Capturing attributes (e.g. size, scale) of NTROs in either repositories or metadata: 44.12% very important
- Populating ORCID profiles with NTROs: 44.12% very important
- Metadata standards, including their application: 57.58% moderately important
- Dealing with multi-item NTROs: 41.18 moderately important
- Dealing with NTROs that include a combination of collaborative and individual work: 52.94 moderately important
- Managing the physical nature of some outputs: 36.36% moderately important
- Dealing with work that is already available online: 44.12% Slightly important

Other areas identified to be addressed by the framework, included: developing community/capacity/support for NTRO creative works; support for researchers across different disciplines; ensuring that the framework is

clear on what is required of the academic in regard to NTROs; emphasis on planning for range of issues before research takes place; definitions of NTROs; CARE principles and separate Indigenous knowledge section; NTRO formats that may emerge in the future; extension of the ERA categories; delivering complex information to time poor researchers; guidance in relation to research statements; promotion on NTROs that can't be shared; consideration of a minimum support model for NTROs; cross departmental collaboration in support of NTROs; institutional recognition and reward structures for NTROs.

Experts/stakeholders

Research

The project interviewed seven stakeholders/experts for their perspectives on issues to do with open research and FAIR as applied to NTROs. This included representatives from key research bodies and prominent relevant figures.

Definition of NTROs

Many respondents commented on the lack of a consistent definition of NTROs and the crudeness of the distinction between traditional and non-traditional outputs. Several respondents noted the limitations of the ERA definition which didn't include software or data and is focused on the arts and humanities. One noted the diversity of material beyond that which was produced for submission as part of ERA.

When asked to define NTROs, one respondent observed that "it's exhibitions, it's your research based websites, its data sets, it's kind of all of the above I guess and also policy output research that forms part of grey literature and whatnot." Another said it was anything other than journal articles, book chapters and monographs. One also observed that it is "anything that a researcher thinks is a research output that is not a journal article." Several respondents associated them with creative or practice research outputs. They were also associated by different respondents with non-text outputs, i.e. exhibitions, artefacts, objects, video, film, software. The notion of "grey literature" arose several times.

One respondent emphasised the importance of a broader cross-sector view and definition if the field was to mature. Several respondents raised the issue of recognition. One said: "Alright, well first of all I hate the term, because I think that by othering every other output apart from scholarly outputs, you are setting yourself up to fail basically, and I prefer the idea of thinking about research outputs writ large."

Several respondents noted how these types of output are not as established within the reward or credit system associated with career progression, funding or policy development. One said they were "a university or academic construct" and referred to outputs that don't fit into the metrics and are not easily measured.

One respondent made the interesting observation that: "It's not necessarily just about individual objects or files, but it's also about a narrative that kind of connects those things together in that narrative, kind of articulates the practice and the method that's been involved in that respect. So it's a combination of individual objects, but also that kind of narrative." They went on to say that it was important therefore how repositories capture and connect these objects.

Challenges

Recognition and legitimacy

One respondent observed how traditional research outputs are already defined and public and how making them open means simply the removal of a paywall. NTROs are not already defined and public in this way so this makes them more complicated. They observed that "one of the biggest obstacles about making NTROs FAIR is actually identifying what the NTRO is".

Another raised the question of the legitimacy of these outputs as existing and having value, particularly because they aren't as measurable in the same way as traditional outputs. For another respondent, this extends to the way repositories may welcome articles, books or conference papers, but fail to acknowledge these other materials.

Copyright

Respondents noted how much more complicated issues of copyright are with, for example, the recording of musical performance between composer, performer and those producing the recording. In discussing FAIR and

Open one respondent noted the importance of assigning a persistent identifier as a minimum but observed the complications involved in assigning a DOI to a performance or a series of performances.

Systems and infrastructure

Quite a few respondents pointed to the diversity of different objects as an important issue as were concerns like storage capacity. A couple of respondents saw a challenge in how the infrastructure and systems are geared to traditional outputs, rather than, for example, portfolios of work. This means you will often not have a sense of the richness of an output. Another observed that if an output is stored on its own it might not be obvious to those outside the field what the research component of the output is. Items may be part of portfolios involving multiple outputs, formats and file types. There are also the complexities of cataloguing such outputs and the challenge of procedures for collecting them.

FAIR

One respondent noted the diversity of academic research practices as a challenge when applying FAIR principles. One respondent in considering the application of FAIR wondered if interoperability really applied to NTROs in the same way as research data for example. They also noted the complications of different licences applying to different components of a work. There may be parts of the work where a quite restrictive licence would be appropriate. They observed: "So I think the challenge really is in applying the FAIR principles appropriately across the huge diversity." They saw FAIR principles as a set of "technical specifications" and there needed to be some consideration as to which applied to NTROs.

Dissemination and discoverability

On the issue of dissemination, one respondent noted the difficulties of coming up with a definition of what or who a publisher of these outputs is. They also noted how the producer of a high profile film is probably not going to make it available open access on a repository. They may however be interested in making extracts or stills available on an institutional repository. There may also be complications from how works are published in collaboration with an outside organisation. Sometimes reports may be made available on organisation websites without metadata or adequate bibliography information.

Another challenge lay in the discoverability of these items, particularly as they often don't appear in Google Scholar in the same way as traditional research outputs since they are often not pdf files. Similarly, resources such as CrossRef focus on text-based outputs.

Re-use

There are further issues with re-use of this material stemming from the complicated copyright issues. These are often unacknowledged by university IP policies. There are difficulties also in Creative Commons licensing and the lack of knowledge on the part of researchers in their application.

Open agenda

One respondent noted how the open agenda is really only just starting to get around to the issue of NTROs. Another observed that the open agenda differs from traditional outputs as there isn't really the incentive to keep things closed. On the other hand, they also suggested that you can't just assume we will make everything open and not think about the complexities involved. Another respondent observed that NTROs and creative outputs are not covered by funder mandates. They are only just getting to book publication now. Another respondent commented that in creative areas there isn't really the urgency to make things open.

Another interviewee expressed disappointment about the way NTROs such as reports had been ignored by the open agenda. They commented that they've been waiting to see the open agenda take notice of reports and discussion papers and policy papers and these kinds of things. They felt that reports or grey literature were regarded as something like predatory publications that could undermine the legitimacy of more established outputs. In terms of FAIR, reports are not catalogued adequately and then don't flow through the system. There is still a standardised bibliographic information flow that doesn't include NTROs.

One respondent raised the issue of repositories in this context noting that some are better than others. There was also the issue of researchers using websites to communicate their research and the associated problems with the preservation of content.

Application of the FAIR principles

Generally, the expert grouping saw that FAIR principles were important, but only partially utilised by repositories that capture different kinds of NTRs. They also noted that the individual elements of FAIR were more or less important when it comes to NTRs. For example, one respondent noted that reuse might not be relevant for some NTRs, especially given the nature of these kinds of outputs.

The use of persistent identifiers was a common issue raised by respondents in applying FAIR principles to NTRs. Specifically DOIs and ORCIDs were both mentioned as ways of making NTRs FAIR and also how support for these was within the remit of libraries. ORCIDs were noted to be a bit of a “hard sell” to creative arts researchers as they don’t really fit their research very well.

In terms of making outputs findable one respondent said “to be bluntly honest, the first thing is just to add them to a repository now”. This also applies to the many NTRs that are not born digitally. It was important to consider how and what metadata gets applied when items are digitised.

The use of licensing was mentioned as being important to making NTRs accessible and reusable. One respondent noted that researchers should “make sure you have a licence so that you’ve protected your ... intellectual output in some sort of way”.

The application of FAIR principles to software has been examined by an RDA working group who found that the FAIR principles only partially applied to software and there were problems in applying them specifically.

Indigenous knowledge

On the issue of Indigenous knowledge, one respondent noted the need for conversations around advocacy. They observed the need for protocols, the need to explain the thinking behind their formulation and make researchers aware of them. Another spoke of the role of the researcher in their connection to Indigenous communities and the extra responsibility this now brings. Another respondent spoke of the need for local experts in this area.

Discussion with this group elicited the observation that research that involves Indigenous people and issues often intersects with a range of issues and focus areas associated with NTRs. The move away from more traditional research paradigms, is evident, for example, from the need to build the capacity of Indigenous communities to undertake and determine the kind of research that will benefit them as a community as opposed to being the subject of research. It therefore raises important issues of Indigenous leadership and governance on research projects; consent and records management; application of ecological knowledge and bio-cultural labels; the importance of knowledge transfer and exchange; cultural awareness and competency training for researchers; research data management; copyright protocols that cover participants; community protocols around access to research and its commercialisation.

This suggests the need for additional investment from universities in an area which challenges the traditional research model along with the need for training researchers in this area. On libraries specifically, this group suggested the need for utilising Indigenous people within the library sector in different working groups. Libraries need policies so that if you are quoting or accessing some material from colonising context you need to distance yourself from views contained there. In handling sensitive material, libraries need to employ protocols around material that refer to deceased Indigenous people. They also need distress protocols for items likely to retraumatise. They need to employ tagging with nation locations. There also needs to be engagement with national organisations like the Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS) on what libraries are putting into place.

Good practice examples

One respondent spoke of “generic” platforms such as Figshare, Zenodo or GitHub as good practice resources for NTROs. They were said to be “getting on with the business of making the infrastructure a bit invisible.” Another spoke of their repository and its ability to manage portfolios or collections of material. This included the ability to add contextual images to text, the ability to hover over an image to see captions and attributions, tabs that allow research narratives and insights, embedded videos etc. They also mentioned the inclusiveness in the naming of their fields: ‘creator’ rather than ‘author,’ ‘description’ rather than ‘abstract,’ ‘commissioning body’ as well as ‘publisher.’ Within the reports area another mentioned APO: Analysis and Policy Observatory. Another respondent spoke of a research project in theatre and film studies which was a curated database of outputs from Australian theatres.

Relevant bodies supporting NTROs

On bodies relevant to NTROs, a couple of respondents mentioned The Academy of Arts and Humanities as well as The Academy of the Social Sciences. Another pointed to the American Geophysical Union. In the UK context, one of our experts identified The Arts and Humanities Research Council as the key funder body. They also pointed to the Practice Research Advisory Group who produced reports around what is practice research and how it can be shared. This latter group is bringing together an “intersection or community practice that isn’t just researchers and practitioners, but also all of the librarians, research data managers, archivists, records managers, research managers.” They noted how NTROs cross more professional areas than is typical of traditional outputs. This conversation needed to happen internationally and include a range of peak bodies concerned with funding research libraries, digital curation etc.

Another respondent also noted the need for a cross sector conversation around these issues, which didn’t seem to be happening in the Australian context. Another observed that the bodies were probably too dispersed and fragmented and there wasn’t a coordinating body. They observed that the ARC has a role, libraries have a role, universities have a role. They also cited professional organisations and Deans organisations. Another observed that there wasn’t one institution that was a custodian of the agenda. One respondent spoke of the importance of a “domain group” such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA) in facilitating a groundswell of support among a community for the development of guidelines and infrastructure particularly in the management of software. Another mentioned the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). AIATSIS was mentioned for Indigenous issues.

Policies and procedures

One respondent commented on the importance of having an open access policy, but noted that the policy needed to be supported by both systems and knowledgeable staff. This includes procedures and workflows, the setting of expectations for the researcher, managing the demand on resources etc. This also needs to address questions around whether this support is going to be self-service, whether there is going to be more hands-on assistance around issues such as copyright, or whether items are going to be archived in the longer term. It is one thing to have a policy and another to be able to deliver on it.

Another suggested that if you value the outputs of your creative people, you don’t need one standard that fits all, but you do have to have some sort of way of assessing what you consider quality. Another spoke of the need to be inclusive when developing policies and guidance so that you are not just referring to traditional outputs. Another spoke of the need to engage these researchers closely as well as understand and embed services. Another spoke of the need for imaginative and creative research communication. Incorporating NTROs within the research impact agenda was seen as a useful way to ensure their inclusion more generally in areas such as policy. One noted there may not be a change in the systems or incentives until there is a sufficient volume of this type of work. This is what led to development in the way research data is being managed.

Validity of NTROs

One respondent suggested that there would be questions about whether NTROs could be regarded as valid research outputs by researchers in traditional areas. There was also the suggestion that those working in the humanities and social sciences might not understand what to do with a data set. One respondent spoke of the need to change the rating scale for valuing NTROs under ERA. Another spoke of the need to put aside the notion of NTROs and streamline the process around research outputs in general. Instead of talking about research data management plans, perhaps we could start talking about research output management.

Library and Institutions

One respondent commented on the importance of relationship building and working with other areas of the university, e.g. the records and archives team, particularly in the area of digital preservation, and noted that libraries are really good at collaborating not only within the university but with other universities and other institutions. They emphasised this collaborative relationship over mere service provision.

One respondent noted the strong repository base within Australian libraries, helping to ensure research outputs are curated and looked after. They noted the need to integrate subject or liaison librarians and to improve advocacy work. This ties with another comment on the library being well placed to involve the academics so work can be properly curated. Another suggested that the library could be involved in helping researchers add their outputs to their staff pages, minting DOIs, getting them to list their outputs on their ORCID page, and that libraries could lean into their core competencies around metadata. There was also a need to lobby ORCID to improve the management of NTROs on their profiles.

There was another observation on the importance of creative arts researchers having the systems to share their research and how this was not there at the moment. There was a need therefore to change repository standards. Spending a lot of time working around systems is not sustainable for researchers. Another suggestion was that we needed something other than a traditional repository to store these outputs, i.e. a separate piece of infrastructure like a media warehouse. Another respondent suggested that there should be a national approach. At the moment there's a lot of investment in local infrastructure, in repositories and libraries, but there is a need for a national collection of these outputs.

There were also a couple of respondents who observed that we are good at making outputs findable and accessible. There was some concern about whether we are there with making them interoperable and practically re-usable with copyright and appropriate licence applied. There is a question about the relevance of interoperability as applied to something like software. Another commented, however, on the way researchers were out there doing their own thing, using their own websites etc, without addressing bibliographic standards required to make them findable. There is not adequate thought as to how such items are recorded. There needs to be some training and guidance around cataloguing effectively.

Final comments included the lack of interoperability that comes with making everything available as a PDF in our repositories. Items need to be pulled apart and manipulated. This respondent also commented on the need to improve digital literacy of library communities to make items interoperable, undertake text and data mining, and use of applications and platforms such as Python and GitHub.

Another spoke on the potential usefulness of having information collected for ERA submission made available on an ongoing basis. They'd like to see this facilitated by a national repository and associated metadata. Yet another interviewee spoke of the need to talk not just to researchers but those making the case for the relevance of NTROs and devising what quality looks like for these outputs.

Another spoke of the need for public interest infrastructure that will be of benefit to the wider community. They observed that academic libraries are becoming less accessible to the community in terms of accessing their collections and accessing knowledge more generally.

Researchers

Research

There were 12 researchers interviewed working in areas ranging in poetry, sound study, improvised music, screenwriting, HIV prevention, arts-based research work, new media, visual art, photography, and astrophysics. Types of NTROs included short VR experiences, audio tracks, (experimental sound, field recordings), poetry, curated exhibitions, live performance, interactive installations, research reports, performance-based works, and film.

Terminology

Many interviewees, particularly from the creative practice areas, expressed some discomfort with the term “non-traditional research outputs”. These were just the research outputs that stemmed from their area. One respondent observed that in the international context these outputs are referred to as creative outputs rather than “non-traditional research outputs”.

Challenges

Recognition

Many respondents commented on the issue of recognition of NTROs as research outputs compared to more traditional research outputs. One researcher commented on the disparity between wider recognition and recognition by the university as the employer of the researcher. Some researchers commented that treating creative outputs as research outputs have been a relatively recent development. There were also questions raised about what specifically is the research component of the creative output. There was also a lack of incentives and recognition for promotion purposes. These frustrations were heightened by lack of promotion for senior academics working in this area. One researcher had to look for funding in Scandinavia rather than locally.

Red tape

There was also frustration about the justifications and “red tape” required to turn them into research outputs. This sometimes results in considerable work to justify the output as research even if it has been peer reviewed. There seemed to be an extra burden of justification around NTROs. Where the researcher is producing both traditional and non-traditional outputs there is a question about how much effort to put into the latter. There was also some frustration with the measures of impact around things like audience size, which doesn’t reflect the importance of the work.

Leadership and vision

One researcher commented on the need for leadership in this area at high levels of the university rather than an exclusive focus on compliance. Another commented that there needs to be some clear direction set by the university around FAIR principles giving direction to researchers about what they want to see done. Another spoke about valuing different types of work in the context of impact and visibility: “I think that we need to value different types of research. We need to value different types of impact.”

Format

Format was nominated as a particular challenge, especially in facilitating access to those who may wish to view these items (e.g. VR experiences). Sometimes these works are ephemeral and capturing digital versions was an issue.

Authorship and intellectual property

Authorship was nominated as another area of difficulty. One researcher working with children regarded works as authored by her subjects and so faced the challenge of attributing ownership over these works. Collaboration and co-design also raises issues of authorship. Another researcher noted the difficulty of quoting creative works within research outputs and the necessary permissions required.

Dissemination and promotion

Some researchers find the idea of publication confusing in the NTRO context. There are a wide variety of outlets for NTROs, e.g. festivals, exhibitions, poetry journals. Researchers also use their own websites although cost was raised as a factor here. One researcher noted the expense of musical distribution, record production and the like. Academic venues for dissemination are perceived as being more limited. Outputs are promoted using social media although there were varying levels of comfort in the use of social media. One researcher noted the growing importance of Instagram for the artistic field.

Searching

There was acknowledgement that the systems for searching NTROs were patchy especially with items sitting on personal websites. When items are published in the repository with a DOI, it still has to be pushed out to networks for distribution. One researcher expressed disappointment that items in the repository were not indexed and displayed in Google Scholar as expected. At least one project team was using Zenodo to make items findable and visible. It is also important for researchers to monitor use and downloads and some were not aware of what the repository does in this area.

Repository/system/platform

There was some comment on the way systems were geared to traditional outputs and there was additional work required by those producing NTROs to make work visible, FAIR and so on. There was a perception that the systems were not really designed for creative works. This meant there was separate and independent effort along with separate systems for NTROs.

One researcher commented on the administrative burden associated with placing NTROs on an institutional repository with little payoff in terms of the dissemination of the work and public reach. There was also some comment on library platforms not being as attractive as some of the available well-designed websites. Repositories just have files attached which you need to download without being able to stream immediately. Researchers producing creative artefacts often want to control the mode of presentation. There are also sometimes restrictions in terms of file sizes. There is some perception that Figshare is an important option.

Re-use

One participant noted that there needs to be more attention from researchers on how items can be shared and re-used and regarded this as a teachable moment.

Measuring engagement

Some researchers had only become belatedly aware of the need to attach DOIs to NTROs to assist with tracking engagement. Many researchers commented on the challenge associated with tracking engagement with NTROs as there weren't the same kind of citation tools available as for traditional outputs. One researcher who generally works in traditional areas thought that one of the biggest challenges was lack of familiarity and ignorance regarding the management of NTROs, particularly having these outputs identified and tracked.

Publishing and promotion patterns

Publication

One researcher observed that publication just meant placing an output into the public realm. Publication can sometimes mean public screening at a festival or on television. There is also some recognition that different channels apply to different types of work and audiences. Prizes, exhibitions and catalogues are also important for artistic works. The imperative to publish can mean concentration on methodological work over artistic practice. Changing modes of publication may mean the form is less important than how it connects to something like research evaluation. There were persistent questions about validity and legitimacy for some researchers. One researcher observed that the major publishers control the versions that are referenced and cited and this is what counts in the long run. A couple of respondents noted the difference between peer

review and self publication. There is a question about whether modes of publication in the NTRO space are often forms of self publication and whether this is valid in the academic context.

Another noted that libraries and research support areas were more attuned to norms of documentation and publication of traditional disciplines rather than the visual arts. This meant that creative researchers were more oriented to their professional communities, commissioning institutions, and curators than to the library as a channel.

Promotion

NTRO researchers report often putting their work to a personal website, blogs, Instagram, YouTube or Twitter and Facebook as a standard way of reaching out to people interested in their work. YouTube is favoured because it shows the number of views. Outputs may be promoted by exhibitions and newsletters.

Audience and open access

Many researchers producing NTROs spoke about quite diverse audiences including the general public. This is regarded as important to the societal and cultural impact of their work. One researcher thought few members of the general public would go to a university repository to access material unless items were pushed out to them. It was important therefore that they were accessible via a Google search. However, they also recognised that academic audiences were quite important in terms of institutional recognition. One researcher involved in the production of reports recognised the importance of open access as a community good. Another researcher saw a downside to open access which they connected to the appropriation of some code without acknowledgement.

Repositories

One researcher was experienced with placing outputs in a subject repository (arXiv) as a resource particularly relevant to their discipline where the metadata is relevant to the field and easily comprehended by those working in the area. Another spoke of using Figshare and Omeka and linking things from their portfolio. Another spoke of the difficulty of submitting to the repository and the fact that they can't provide a DOI and lack of preservation policy.

Indigenous knowledge

Quite a few of the researchers had engaged with Indigenous knowledge issues in the course of their projects, although not as central features of their research. They spoke about these aspects of their projects with some passion and engagement. The production of NTROs appears to be a prominent aspect of this kind of engagement. Projects included astrophysics research that contained an Indigenous community perspective on issues to do with mythology and the night sky, the mapping of publications on Indigenous-related themes that had been made open access and studies of Indigenous health. This has produced reports, databases, film, art exhibitions and other creative work.

Protocols mentioned by researchers included acknowledgement, the involvement of Indigenous researchers and organisations, and deferring to colleagues with expertise in the area. One researcher described the challenge as involving questioning of the

“Western model of knowledge where you are the author and you have some kind of ownership and can manage the expression of the work. That's not how it works right in the First Nations context, and you have to be engaged with a much broader range of people, and there's no sort of release point at which you can say that's the end of your accountability and it now goes out into the world to be done with what the world thinks should happen with it. It always sweeps back to the specific kind of place where it is, and I think that's a big challenge for all of us”

HDRs

Quite a few interviewees noted the way HDR students may be engaged in both a traditional written component and a non-traditional creative work. One of the challenges was in the framing of and justifying the NTRO as research, with one participant observing:

Your creative practice research has to be formulated in some way that you know she is able to answer a research question. So yeah, it sits within some sort of structure... I think it just comes down to making sure you've got a clear research question and then a methodology that supports... new understanding or new knowledge.

In the non-creative areas, there was more emphasis on the HDR completing the thesis. One participant observed that the production of an NTRO such as a report might be done by a HDR only if they had time and capacity. It may not be as essential as the production of a PhD thesis. There was still quite a lot of emphasis on traditional publication for HDRs.

Several participants mentioned the issue of research dissemination for HDRs producing NTROs. One researcher felt that HDR NTROs don't really get recognised (or captured in the repository) in the same way as traditional research dissemination. Several respondents noted that advice around research dissemination was important for HDRs. While it was important for them to take part in exhibitions, prizes and awards, they are not necessarily looking to the library to assist with this.

One researcher observed that libraries hold the written dissertation, but was less sure about documentation around exhibitions or the creative work itself. Another put this down to the artistic PhD being a relatively recent development and support was still unformed. Another suggested because their work was not collected by ERA the university was less interested in it.

Institutional support

Faculty support mainly came in the form of organisation of ERA submissions of NTROs. This includes the management of systems for ERA submissions, the provision of workshops and training, peer review, and assistance in writing of abstracts and research statements. There did seem to be some variation in levels of support or even recognition of NTROs depending on the institutional context. There was also an issue around how complex and user friendly the systems were to use. One researcher observed that the submission form required substantial justification for NTROs that weren't required for traditional outputs and this operated as a disincentive. Another observed that there was little support beyond ERA. This raises some interesting questions around ongoing support in the post-ERA period.

There was also a question about institutional will around FAIR and open given lack of strong mandates and the need for protecting IP and commercialisation. One participant observed that it is important to display understanding of the "life worlds" of the creative area when engaging them about issues of open and FAIR.

In terms of the research office, there is a perception that there may be some support available there, but that the focus is on traditional research outputs. There is a perception that reports and creative outputs require substantial work in establishing evidence of their quality and impact. There are millions of dollars involved in grants in some of the traditional areas. There is also a strong emphasis on commercialisation over open from within these areas.

Incentives

The overwhelming feeling was that there was a lack of institutional incentive for making NTROs open and FAIR. This was particularly so with regard to promotion. Several respondents noted that there isn't the kind of incentive there is to publish in highly-ranked journals. There aren't NTRO journals included in the relevant journal lists. One researcher perceived that the production of reports was regarded by the university as a bit of a distraction compared to highly-ranked journals. Another noted how the ephemeral nature of creative works is not conducive to research recognition.

Library support

General

There is both an emphasis on the general supportiveness of the library and not necessarily looking to the library to support in these particular areas. One participant emphasised the interdisciplinary position of the library in being able to pull different people together from across the university to solve particular problems.

Things valued

When asked about things researchers valued about the library, this included assistance with researcher profiles as part of dissemination of outputs; assistance with research metrics in establishing evidence of scholarly impact; knowledge of licences and copyright; assistance from the repository team in the development of workflows; library involvement in strategic planning for the research area; the provision of a repository and the associated indexing and metadata; and support for graduate researchers.

Copyright and licensing

When asked about copyright and licensing support many assumed the library could assist but weren't very clear about how. There were also some mixed feelings about whether it was appropriate for the library to support in this area as it suggested questions of IP and commercialisation for some.

Researcher profiles

Most researchers registered some awareness of the usefulness of having an ORCID and university's encouragement to have researchers register. There was some recognition that the library could assist but this wasn't universal. One researcher said they don't really use it because they don't publish in journals and another responded positively at the idea that there could be help with NTROs and researcher IDs.

Promotion

Most didn't see the Library as having a significant role in the promotion of NTROs.

Repository

Researchers regarded the collection of outputs in one place in a kind of portfolio as a useful function of the repository, as was the attached metadata in making the research searchable along with the long-term preservation of those outputs. One researcher said they were unaware of whether the repository contained NTROs. One researcher has observed that there is a need for integrated digital systems and platforms that would manage and represent all aspects of the research output.

Recognition as research

One researcher commented on how it was assumed by the library that their outputs would form part of the cultural collection rather than being treated like other research outputs.

Research statements

There wasn't much knowledge that the library may support the writing of research statements as opposed to just doing it themselves. Another researcher recalls that writing research statements was a mystery and a challenge when they first started.

Evidencing engagement

There wasn't any significant perception of a role for the library in assisting to provide evidence of engagement. One researcher mentioned consulting the library on different options for providing evidence of impact but decided they didn't have the time to do this properly.

FAIR principles

There was a degree of recognition that the library had a role in the promotion of open and FAIR principles particularly through their online guides. One researcher cited a research data champions program that helped

in the promotion of data literacy. They detected some reluctance to embrace such principles among colleagues because of IP issues.

Metadata

There was some recognition that the library assists with metadata, although some researchers were unaware that they could look to the library for help here.

DOI

While there is good awareness of the importance of assigning a DOI, some researchers felt it was an involved and difficult process.

Archiving and preservation

Some researchers were not really thinking about long-term preservation and archiving of material. One researcher, with some familiarity with the library, noted the lack of a preservation policy or strategy.

Levels of access

Most researchers acknowledged managing access as an issue, but weren't generally looking to the library to assist with this. One researcher working in the film area gave as an example the restriction of access to a film prior to being made available in film festivals.

Onboarding

One researcher noted that onboarding support focused on the production end of research rather than dissemination. Another noted that they became familiar with the research process around NTROs in an ad hoc way and thought the library could probably assist with this. The Library was felt to be an interdisciplinary space where some of the research assistance could be developed.

Industry standard

Many participants were impressed by the range of issues brought up by this project and expressed interest in following up with their libraries about some of these. Finally one researcher wished there was an industry standard for the kind of support libraries could provide in the area of NTROs:

It would actually be nice if there was even a place just to understand maybe what some other institutions are doing, so that there is language and I could go to my institution and say, do you do this because I think at this point, I don't even know what to ask for. So if that was something that would be possible, that would be lovely.

Libraries

Definition

ERA definitions figured strongly in how libraries define NTROs. Some respondents said they were anything that isn't a traditional output and this included creative works and portfolios. Another discussed the flexibility of the term, how creative works were broken down and the inclusion of different types of reports. There was also discussion of types of grey literature in the repository that are not strictly research outputs (but could presumably extend from research projects and interests). There was also a comment on the way research data is treated as a specific output rather than an NTRO.

Visibility

Some libraries only make ERA outputs available in the repository. One respondent noted that researchers often don't provide more than a title and a date for NTROs so they are unable to make it available in the repository. They also raised the issue of research statements which are meant to be provided for NTROs and how often it is not possible to determine what the research content of an NTRO is without publicly accessible research statements. If they don't wish to make these statements public then the repository will still need a description of the research content. This statement is either added to the description field or attached as an administration file. Another respondent noted how the repository pushes things out to Trove or to the staff profiles.

Recognition

On questions of recognition and validity of NTROs, one respondent noted that these outputs are not monetised in the same way, and don't attract the same funding so are not regarded as much of a priority. A couple of libraries report that where these relate to high profile research areas they are regarded as important and legitimate. One library reported that they also have a Q1 equivalent tag applied to NTROs by the relevant department. After the collection of NTROs there was some review of these items in terms of ERA eligibility, but this was less straightforward than with traditional outputs. Another spoke about how their open access policy recognised all outputs and mandated their availability.

Copyright

Copyright is regarded by libraries as one of the most significant issues in connection with NTROs. In particular the issue of multiple copyright owners for creative works is important. There is an educational task around this and a challenge to make it as simple as possible.

Custodianship

One library reported that they have researchers creating websites and databases and repositories and wanting support from the library to host and manage these. There is a feeling that this is not purely a library issue and needs to be addressed at an institutional level.

Repository

Submission and workflow

Most libraries described a workflow involving the researcher uploading an output and associated metadata, the attachment of a research statement, review for ERA eligibility, and checks for copyright. There were usually no options for researcher self publishing without a process of review and curation. One library commented that they are still figuring out what qualifies as a research output in this space: "Someone may come and want to submit an exhibition but did they do the whole exhibition and is this the first time it has been exhibited, i.e. is it new research?"

One library described work to improve the workflow observing that it was initially quite convoluted with "lots of emails and files and folders chasing back and forth". They then brought different areas together and used a software solution that employed forms and workflows. This system would ask the researcher for information depending on research output type, would give them the opportunity to upload the output and any associated

evidence. These were then reviewed by the nominated academic unit before progressing to peer review. The library then assesses the item for sharing publicly (the researcher indicates whether they want this shared) and stores the item for preservation purposes.

Labels

Some pointed to label options made available by the systems with very limited customisations rather than use ERA classifications. Some libraries put these outputs under “other” or “creative works” because of the limitations of the systems. Generally, NTROs may appear under different categories even if there is a specific tag for NTROs. There was some recognition that the ERA classifications may be subject to revision in any case. Sometimes a field can be created specifically for entering the ERA classifications or a field for NTRO details. In one instance, these hadn’t been mapped as formal tags mainly because of the IT support that would be required. Fields like the description field are sometimes used as workarounds, but this is not without problems as this field in one instance is publicly viewable but not searchable. There are some additional local MARC fields for NTROs, e.g. a field to hold the research statement.

Researcher support

In terms of researcher support, one library reported that they were waiting for a set of university guidelines to be developed around NTROs so this would set a framework for their work with the research office and for the education and promotion of FAIR principles in the university. Another library spoke of the need to support the legitimacy of NTROs as research outputs. They thought it was important for researchers to be thinking and planning to make outputs open from the very beginning. They identified the need for early promotion of open research at the graduate research level. They noted low awareness of Creative Commons licensing in support of accessibility and re-use. They also aimed for all NTROs in the next ERA round to have DOIs and said they would use DataCite for this. Another library pointed to the need for support in Indigenous knowledge issues and copyright. Another said that researchers need support around the ERA requirements but also around wider issues such as impact and needed to connect this with open. They went on to discuss how they provide online support, and how their liaison librarians will provide workshops and presentations to different groups. They also mentioned talking with HDRs although most of these are not involved in producing NTROs.

Open and copyright

Several libraries emphasised the importance of education around open and associated issues such as copyright and cited some achievements in this area. There was also a need to reassure researchers who were concerned about Intellectual Property issues. Most libraries spoke about the layers of copyright, multiple copyrights and competing ownerships. Researchers needed the appropriate permissions particularly with regard to third party material. There were also issues of privacy, cultural sensitivity, and issues arising from pre-existing availability of material.

In at least one instance, these kinds of issues were dealt with on an ad hoc basis. Another pointed out that while NTROs might be about 20% of the submitted items, they take up about 80% of our time to process because of complications and the fact that we can’t just point to a published version. Most libraries have a copyright officer to help advise in this area. Libraries don’t, however, have the resources to track down the complications of copyright ownership associated with outputs and are dependent on the researcher here. Most researchers are unwilling to do this. Libraries are employing reference guides that cover this kind of issue, as well as outlining paths to open. One respondent noted that if there were concerns about an output then the item was locked down without much discussion with the researcher. On the other hand, another library respondent thought that there is usually something we can disseminate associated with the research project. Another spoke of this area in terms of risk management, i.e. acceptance that there may be the need to take down items if there was a complaint.

Licensing and re-use

There is recognition of the close connection between the complications of copyright and the issues of licensing and re-use. The application of Creative Commons licences may also involve multiple copyright owners. The

application of a Creative Commons licence is also usually a policy gap at the university level. Raising the issue of licensing also tends to provoke a level of wariness among creative practice researchers that may require a kind of cultural shift on the part of relevant researchers.

Indigenous knowledge

Among the different libraries we spoke to it was clear that this area was still emergent and libraries and universities generally were only beginning to come to terms with the issues involved. There was a general feeling that the library needed to work with groups outside the library to develop approaches to Indigenous knowledge. For one library, the focus so far includes Indigenous knowledge labels which would involve an advisory group determining appropriate labels. Another library referred to the potential usefulness of something that could structure conversations with Indigenous communities to have ownership over the outputs.

There was recognition that Indigenous knowledge issues were going to add to the complexity of working with this material along with necessary resourcing. There was strong support for highlighting research done in this area through the use of tagging. At least one library pointed to an option to nominate an item as containing Indigenous knowledge at the submission stage. Libraries would usually call on expertise within the university in dealing with any expressed need by researchers regarding Indigenous knowledge issues. Sometimes there is a request to redact parts of an item for reasons of cultural sensitivity.

Institutional context

Libraries find it useful to have wider institutional guidelines, structures and policies covering NTRs, but their presence depends on different institutional contexts. NTRs may be mentioned in different policies related to IP, open access etc. Different arrangements reported include an advisory group reporting to the research committee, staff focusing on this area within the research office, institutional guidelines, a group looking at Q1 internal equivalence tags for internal use only (e.g. promotion). The library may be involved in the development, maintenance and review of different processes to differing degrees depending on the institution. One library also reported appointing an ERA librarian close to submission time for the ERA round whose role is the gathering of outputs. There is a lot of work in support of NTRs because of the different issues associated with these.

Libraries

Libraries are reporting that there isn't much connection made institutionally between funder mandates and researchers abiding by FAIR principles. In terms of training in FAIR, the repository area may be just providing 'as-needed' assistance with some online guides to provide advice, whereas the liaison area is providing more outreach services and the provision of workshops. In terms of support for researchers, respondents mentioned workshops and drop-in sessions, representation on research committees and onboarding for new researchers. The need for preservation was also raised by one library.

Projects planned

In terms of projects planned, libraries mentioned work to separate and distinguish different creative outputs, education for researchers, thinking about the library role as custodians of research outputs and how this can be made sustainable. Many libraries and universities were now emphasising the importance of a sustainability lens. There is recognition that making these outputs findable and accessible is more straightforward than making them interoperable and re-usable. Another library wants to focus on assigning DOIs to these outputs. Another spoke of highlighting Indigenous research. There is a sense in which some libraries are hesitant about NTRs because of the risks and difficulties associated with copyright and licensing. Several libraries have identified a need for copyright literacy and thinking about IP issues from the start rather than untangling the problems down the track.

Framework

Libraries nominated Indigenous knowledge as something they'd like to see in the framework given the current uncertainty around this. Another spoke of the need for a community of practice approach to helping with professional development in this area. Some libraries wanted to see how we support the research lifecycle, including the things researchers should be thinking about at each stage and some educational resources that can be used.

Discussion

Findings can be grouped against a range of broad themes. Drawing together issues and themes from across the research informs the development of the framework and can be broadly characterised in the following way:

Terminology

During the course of the study the project found the term “Non-traditional research output” quite common in Australia and New Zealand but less so elsewhere. International discussion was usually framed around creative or practice-based research. The definition employed by the Australian Research Council (ARC) is a key reference point for libraries and researchers.

The project group notes that non-traditional research outputs differ from traditional research outputs such as scholarly monographs or peer-reviewed journal articles. NTRs are frequently, although not exclusively, the product of creative or practice-based research projects and practices. There are indeed a wide variety of disciplines that create NTRs across the research lifecycle making it difficult to posit an exact and encompassing definition. NTRs are frequently the research products of different kinds of critical endeavour that see the development of new concepts, understandings, methodologies often in new and creative forms. Examples of NTRs given by ERA include creative works, performance, recorded/rendered works, curated exhibitions or events, research reports, portfolios. NTRs can also include software, coding, website creation, databases, and commissioned reports of various kinds.

Part of the challenge follows from defining NTRs in opposition to traditional publication outputs rather than working with a more inclusive definition of research outputs as an accessible presentation of research findings in their many forms and formats. Many from the expert group noted the crudeness of the distinction between traditional and non-traditional research outputs and the limitations of the ERA definition of NTRs.

The ERA definition figured strongly in how libraries were defining the term although there was some question about whether it encompasses grey literature and research data. The literature as well as discussion with experts and researchers underlined some of the inadequacies of this term. The environmental scan revealed that a range of definitions were used by different libraries. Researchers also expressed some discomfort with the term as these were just their outputs.

Recognition and legitimacy

There was a strong sense in the literature as well as interviews across the different groups that NTRs were undervalued compared to more traditional outputs. One article observed that the distinction between traditional and non-traditional research output was often regarded as a distinction between formal and informal publications. There was some comment in the literature that the diversification of publishing activity as a result of digital technologies provided an opportunity for broadening our conception and understanding of publishing. The environmental scan revealed very uneven mention of NTRs on library websites, guides and repositories. The survey revealed a high degree of recognition for NTRs.

The expert/stakeholder group noted that these works were not measurable in the same way as traditional outputs. There was a lot of comment by researchers on the extra work and justification required to put them forward as research outputs. Some researchers commented on the disparity between the wider recognition their work had received and the recognition received by their university as their employer.

Issues and challenges in handling NTRs

The literature draws attention to some of the inherent aspects of NTRs that make them complicated to handle. This includes how outputs often involve multiple items, the way the work can involve individual and collaborative work, the complexity of size and scale, the prevalence of versions and iterations, copyright complexity, the need for additional metadata, measuring impact, archiving and long-term preservation, and identifying research components.

The expert/stakeholder group nominated copyright as a particularly complicated issue, along with issues around infrastructure and systems, dissemination and re-use of NTROs. The researcher group raised “red tape” issues around the justification of their work as research, the lack of leadership in the management of NTROs at a university level, the need to facilitate access to different formats, authorship and IP issues, the question of what constitutes publication, the ability to search for and access NTROs, the lack of understanding around re-use, the inadequacy of repository platforms and measuring engagement. The Library group nominated issues such as copyright and licensing, workflow issues, labelling, cultural sensitivity and privacy.

FAIR and Open

The issues raised by FAIR in particular include persistent identifiers, rich metadata, open licences, and provenance information. There is low awareness about FAIR in the humanities raising the need for training and advocacy. There are legal issues with regard to sensitive information and property rights around re-use. The environmental scan revealed that NTROs don’t feature strongly in relation to open or FAIR information on the library websites or guides. In general FAIR principles are discussed in relation to research data only. The expert/stakeholder group raised the question of whether interoperability or re-use applies to NTROs. One respondent from this group also noted that the issues of openness were only just getting around to addressing NTROs. They observed that you can’t just assume everything will be open and not address the complexities involved. NTROs are also not covered by funder mandates in the way traditional outputs are.

Library support for persistent identifiers as well as licensing support were regarded as important in this context. Library respondents noted the need to reassure researchers about IP issues when making their research open. Libraries noted a wariness by researchers about licensing. In the context of complicated copyright issues, libraries noted the resource intensive nature of support for NTROs.

Institutional context

Within the institutional context, the environmental scan revealed that mention of the NTROs within open access policies tended to be limited. The survey indicated that while there was mention of NTROs in policies and procedures, there was not an emphasis at an institutional level on making NTROs open and FAIR and that this mainly fell to the library.

Researchers saw institutional support in this area as connected to ERA submission. This kind of support varied according to institutional context. This included assistance around the writing of research statements. One of the pain points here was around workflows for ERA submissions. There was a lack of institutional priority given to the issues of open and FAIR with the priority for commercialisation taking precedence. Libraries find it useful to have wider institutional guidelines and policies around support for NTROs. The ERA process also provided a focus of institutional collaboration for libraries in support of NTROs. Libraries may need to look for new opportunities to work and collaborate in this space with the cessation of ERA.

Library support

The environmental scan revealed that there is generally little mention of library support for NTROs. There is some mention of repository support for creative works and reports. There is also some mention of library support for writing research statements. There is also little mention of other areas of the university who can assist with NTROs. The survey reported that a little less than half of the libraries were involved in the ERA reporting process and support for NTRO reporting as part of that. A greater proportion did work with the research office on initiatives related to NTROs.

The survey indicated that there was a broad range of library advice, training, resourcing, and direct assistance in application of FAIR to NTROs. This included knowledge of FAIR principles, open access publishing, researcher profiles, licences and copyright, application of metadata, use of persistent identifiers, publication support, preservation, access, dissemination, writing research statements, and identifying engagement and impact. This support was provided via a consultation and advice service, use of guides and videos, presentations and workshops.

The expert/stakeholder group held the view that libraries should draw on their experience in collaborating with other areas of the university when supporting NTROs. They also noted the strong repository base and experience as an important resource. They noted the need to draw in librarians for advocacy work in this area, and the need to provide support with regard to researcher profiles. They further noted the need for cross-sector conversation about the issues around FAIR and open NTROs, similar to what had been achieved in the research data space.

Researchers expect to control the curation of their work, and desire assistance on issues such as author rights and file types and researcher profiles, and want to see metadata that reflects significance and impact. They want to present their work with visual impact. There was a need to work with researchers around copyright and licensing. In general researchers looked to the library for assistance in the use of researcher profiles, metrics, repository support, the use of metadata. They were less aware of what the library might help with copyright issues, the writing of research statements, archiving and preservation.

Library interviewees regarded copyright as one of the biggest challenges in support of NTROs. They noted the low awareness among researchers in Creative Commons licensing and issues of sharing and re-use.

Indigenous knowledge

Indigenous knowledge issues are particularly important to NTROs. The environmental scan revealed that CARE principles are mainly discussed in terms of research data and that there was little information on Indigenous knowledge and NTROs. The survey revealed only a small number of libraries had developed guidelines that include making NTROs FAIR and open. Issues that libraries had identified as relevant to Indigenous knowledge included access management, platforms designed to share results with Indigenous communities, Creative Commons licensing that included Indigenous knowledge labels.

The expert/stakeholder group noted the intersections between research involving Indigenous issues and NTROs, particularly given the movement away from traditional research paradigms. There were important issues around Indigenous leadership and governance on research projects; consent and records management; application of ecological knowledge and bio-cultural labels; the importance of knowledge transfer and exchange; cultural awareness and competency training for researchers; research data management; copyright protocols that cover participants; community protocols around access to research and its commercialisation. They also identified a number of focus areas for library action including employment of Indigenous people, protocols for handling sensitive materials, use of Indigenous knowledge labels and engagement with organisations such as AIATSIS.

It was noticeable that many of the research interests of our researcher group touched on Indigenous issues and the high level of interest by researchers that they do this. Protocols mentioned by researchers included acknowledgement, the involvement of Indigenous researchers and organisations, and deferring to colleagues with expertise in the area. It was clear that this is still an emergent issue for libraries and universities generally. There was strong support for highlighting research in this area, but acknowledgement that it would add to the resource intensive nature of support for NTROs.

Repositories

There was an argument within the literature that repositories have a role in enhancing the management of these kinds of output. Benefits included good curation and management to meet funder requirements, enhancing discoverability, research transparency, facilitating collaborative opportunities, allowing tracking and impact, connecting work on websites with institutional visibility, legitimacy and endorsement, preservation, managing access. There is some comment in the literature, nevertheless, that NTROs are not generally a significant part of repository holdings. The survey revealed that volume ranged from 50 items to several thousand. This is partly because relevant researchers are focused on disseminating their work beyond the university context, and because rewards and recognition also lay outside the university system. The expert/stakeholder group confirmed these observations. The literature also noted researcher concerns about

intellectual property in the context of open, lack of understanding about the repository, concern about whether the repository will display material adequately, and the administrative burden of adding such material to the repository. Some repositories also limit their holdings to ERA items.

While the environmental scan suggested that most repositories didn't have publicly accessible collection policies, the survey did provide some links to policies. Repositories often refer to NTRs as output types within submission information. The scan also revealed that Figshare is sometimes used for NTRs. The expert/stakeholder group observed that some repositories are better than others in the presentation and management of NTRs. The survey indicated that most libraries didn't use a different metadata schema to traditional outputs.

The expert/stakeholder group noted the need for libraries to advocate for a change to repository standards to better support NTRs. They also identified the need for a national collection of these kinds of research outputs. There was a general need to focus on workflows, deposit options and system integrations to streamline the collection process. There was a need for metadata that contextualises and gives greater descriptive information for the work. Library respondents also identified workflows around the submission process as one of the significant issues in repository support. They also regarded labels and tagging as significant issues.

Publishing

The survey of libraries revealed an assumption by some that the institutional repository was the most common way in which NTRs were published and made visible, although there was also recognition that there was actually no standard way of publishing NTRs. In this context there was mention of personal and institutional websites, video platforms such as YouTube and the sites of partner institutions. The survey also indicated that there wasn't a strong institutional emphasis on making NTRs open and that the messaging on open generally came from the library. There was a comment also that open access to NTRs was sometimes limited by performing rights, commercial considerations and copyright.

The researcher group emphasised the diversity of channels in which NTRs can be "published." There was some anxiety about whether many of these channels constitute a form of self publication and how this is regarded by traditional publication models based on peer review. Many researchers utilise social media platforms in the promotion of their research and platforms such as YouTube. Many researchers wish to connect with diverse audiences including the general public, although they recognised that academic recognition is also very important. They also have some experience placing material in third-party repositories.

Incentives

The survey reported a lack of incentives around making NTRs open. Open was generally not a criteria for promotions or performance reviews. Several interviewees from the expert/stakeholder group noted how these types of output are not as established within the reward or credit system associated with career progression, funding or policy development. The researcher group noted a lack of incentives around making NTRs open or FAIR. One researcher felt that the production of reports was seen as a distraction.

Policies and procedures

The expert/stakeholder group noted the importance of open access policies but emphasised the importance of having the systems and knowledgeable staff to support these policies. The overall emphasis on this group here was not to assume that issues would be the same as for traditional research outputs and the need to engage researchers closely. Issues around research impact were regarded as particularly important.

Research statements and research impact

The literature also points to the research statement as being important to the recognition of NTRs as research outputs. There is also some discussion about the way creative arts point to the need for broad social and cultural impact over academic impact. Researchers are generally unaware of how the library might

support them in this area. These statements are an important part of making such research outputs publicly accessible via the institutional repository.

HDRs

The researcher group recognised a challenge for HDRs in identifying and articulating the research component of the NTRO. They also saw the need for advice and support in the dissemination of the research findings.

Framework (Recommendations)

The project recommends the adoption of the framework for library support of FAIR and Open Non-Traditional Research Outputs. The Framework is structured according to different phases of the research lifecycle so as to identify issues and needs from the researcher's perspective. These phases are then incorporated into the three areas of Pre-Production, Production and Post-Production.

Within each of the phases, the framework is further structured according to different facets: the 'Focus area'; the 'Aims' involved in focussing on and developing this area; broader 'Advocacy/Enablement' issues raised by this area; and finally, the 'Tiered Service' considerations.

Focus areas have been mapped to that part of the lifecycle where they become particularly prominent as concerns, while recognising that many of these issues cross the different phases of the research lifecycle. The Framework outlines the aims associated with each focus area. It also considers a more general advocacy and enablement aspect that Libraries may want to consider, often relating to collaborations, policy, or infrastructure development. A tiered approach to service support is designed to allow flexibility in how libraries develop services.

The issues are further broken down into Introductory, Intermediate and Advanced phases in recognition of the different stages of maturity for different library services. This allows Libraries to consider and adopt different aspects of the framework according to opportunity, interest and resourcing. Libraries that are new to NTRO support may wish to consider the introductory elements initially; the intermediate section is for those that have mastered the basics and wish to extend their support; the advanced for those who already offer great support and wish to ensure nothing has been missed.

The final part of each section includes resources that have been identified as good practice examples.

The Framework is intended to provide guidance to CAUL member libraries about how to increase the proportion of NTROs by Australian university researchers that are appropriately described, archived, preserved and made accessible.

Further recommendations

In addition to adoption of the Framework the project suggests the following overall recommendations for the sector:

- Adoption of a broad and inclusive definition of NTROs.
- Adoption of conception of FAIR and CARE that looks beyond research data to research outputs in general.
- Promote the idea of research output management plans beyond just RDM.
- Contribute to the ongoing development of protocols for libraries in handling research outputs related to Indigenous knowledge that encompass authorship, citation, repository presentation, copyright, licensing, access.
- Facilitate discussion of repository requirements for managing and presenting NTROs.
- Consider strategies to facilitate development of national collection of NTROs.
- Development of collective resources, e.g. guides across universities in support of NTROs.
- Facilitate cross sector conversation of FAIR, CARE and open as applies to NTROs, eg community of practice conversation.
- Lobby ORCID to improve their management of NTROs.

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